

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
COMPANY VISITOR MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
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ABSTRACT

Company Visitor Management System deals with the security provided at company premises from the unauthenticated or unwanted visitors.

Nowadays, in most organizations Visitor management consists of visitors— scribbling their name in a paper book.

Instead, Company Visitor Management System will assist you the professionalized way in which you welcome your visitors. This software is a complete Visitor Management service to improve the efficiency, productivity, security.

This is the project which keep records of visitors who visited in the company. CVMS has one module i.e admin. Dashboard: In this sections, admin can briefly view how many visitors visited in a particular period.

Visitors: In this section, admin adds new visitors by filling their information in add visitors sections and also view and manage visitors records. Admin also put visitors out time in the manage records section.

Search: In this bar, admin can search a particular person by their name and phone number.

Reports: In this section admin can generate visitors reports between two dates. Admin can also update his profile, change password and recover password.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Introduction:

Company Visitor Management system is a web-based technology that will revolutionize the way your company manages visitors. Visitor Management system is more important to security guards or security company. This web application provides a way to effectively control record & track company visitor traffic.

In CVMS we use PHP and MySQL database. This is the project which keeps records of visitors who visited in the company. **CVMS has one module i.e. admin**

1. **Dashboard:** In this sections, admin can briefly view how many visitors visited in a particular period.
2. **Visitors:** In this section, admin adds new visitors by filling their information in add visitors sections and also view and manage visitor's records. Admin also put visitors out time in the manage records section.
3. **Search:** In this bar, admin can search a particular person by their name and phone number.
4. **Reports:** In this section admin can generate visitor's reports between two dates.

Admin can also update his profile, change password and recover password.

Purpose:-

The purpose of developing company visitor management system is to computerized the tradition way of visitors. Another purpose for developing this application is to generate the report automatically.

Scope:-

Company Visitor Management System project is developed as a web application and it will work over web.

CHAPTER 2 REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

Hardware Configuration :

Client Side:

RAM	512 MB
Hard disk	10 GB
Processor	1.0 GHz

Server side:

RAM	1 GB
Hard disk	20 GB
Processor	2.0 GHz

Software Requirement:

Client Side:

Web Browser	Google Chrome or any compatible browser
Operating System	Windows or any equivalent OS

Server Side:

Web Server	APACHE
Server side Language	PHP5.6 or above version
Database Server	MYSQL
Web Browser	Google Chrome or any compatible browser
Operating System	Windows or any equivalent OS

APACHE

The Apache HTTP Server Project is an effort to develop and maintain an open-source HTTP server for modern operating systems including UNIX and Windows. The goal of this project is to provide a secure, efficient and extensible server that provides HTTP services in sync with the current HTTP standards.

The Apache HTTP Server ("httpd") was launched in 1995 and it has been the most popular web server on the Internet since April 1996. It has celebrated its 20th birthday as a project in February 2015.

PHP

- ✓ PHP stands for PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor.
- ✓ PHP is a server-side scripting language, like ASP.
- ✓ PHP scripts are executed on the server.
- ✓ PHP supports many databases (MYSQL, Informix, Oracle, Sybase, Solid, Generic ODBC, etc.).

- ✓ PHP is an open source software .
- ✓ PHP is free to download and use.

MYSQL

- ✓ MYSQL is a database server
- ✓ MYSQL is ideal for both small and large applications
- ✓ MYSQL supports standard SQL
- ✓ MYSQL compiles on a number of platforms
- ✓ MYSQL is free to download and use
- ✓ How to access MySQL:

<http://localhost/phpmyadmin>

CHAPTER 3

ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

Analysis:

In present all visitor work done on the paper. The whole year visitor is stored in the registers. We can't generate reports as per our requirements because its take more time to calculate the visitors report.

Disadvantage of present system:

- **Not user friendly:** The present system not user friendly because data is not stored in structure and proper format.
- **Manual Control:** All report calculation is done manually so there is a chance of error.
- **Lots of paper work:** Visitors maintain in the register so lots of paper require storing details.
- **Time consuming**

CHAPTER 4

DESIGN INTRODUCTION

Design is the first step in the development phase for any techniques and principles for the purpose of defining a device, a process or system in sufficient detail to permit its physical realization.

Once the software requirements have been analyzed and specified the software design involves three technical activities - design, coding, implementation and testing that are required to build and verify the software.

The design activities are of main importance in this phase, because in this activity, decisions ultimately affecting the success of the software implementation and its ease of maintenance are made. These decisions have the final bearing upon reliability and maintainability of the system. Design is the only way to accurately translate the customer's requirements into finished software or a system.

Design is the place where quality is fostered in development. Software design is a process through which requirements are translated into a representation of software. Software design is conducted in two steps. Preliminary design is concerned with the transformation of requirements into data

UML Diagrams:

Actor:

A coherent set of roles that users of use cases play when interacting with the use cases.

Use case: A description of sequence of actions, including variants, that a system performs that yields an observable result of value of an actor.

UML stands for Unified Modeling Language. UML is a language for specifying, visualizing and documenting the system. This is the step while developing any product after analysis. The goal from this is to produce a model of the entities involved in the project which later need to be built. The representation of the entities that are to be used in the product being developed need to be designed.

USECASE DIAGRAMS:

Use case diagrams model behavior within a system and helps the developers understand of what the user require. The stick man represents what's called an actor.

Use case diagram can be useful for getting an overall view of the system and clarifying who can do and more importantly what they can't do.

Use case diagram consists of use cases and actors and shows the interaction between the use case and actors.

- The purpose is to show the interactions between the use case and actor.
- To represent the system requirements from user's perspective.
- An actor could be the end-user of the system or an external system.

USECASE DIAGRAM:

A Use case is a description of set of sequence of actions. Graphically it is rendered as an ellipse with solid line including only its name. Use case diagram is a behavioral

diagram that shows a set of use cases and actors and their relationship. It is an association between the use cases and actors. An actor represents a real-world object. Primary Actor – Sender, Secondary Actor Receiver.

Use Case Diagrams:

Class Diagram:

A description of set of objects that share the same attributes operations, relationships, and semantics

Column Name	Data Type
ID	int(5)
AdminName	varchar(45)
UserName	char(45)
MobileNumber	bigint(11)
Email	varchar(120)
Password	varchar(120)
AdminRegdate	timestamp

Column Name	Data Type
ID	int(5)
FullName	varchar(120)
Email	varchar(120)
MobileNumber	bigint(11)
Address	varchar(250)
WhomtoMeet	varchar(120)
Department	varchar(120)
ReasontoMeet	varchar(120)
EnterDate	timestamp
remark	varchar(255)
outtime	timestamp

ER Diagram:

The Entity-Relationship (ER) model was originally proposed by Peter in 1976 [Chen76] as a way to unify the network and relational database views. Simply stated the ER model is a conceptual data model that views the real world as entities and relationships. A basic component of the model is the Entity-Relationship diagram which is used to visually represent data objects. Since Chen wrote his paper the model

has been extended and today it is commonly used for database design for the database designer, the utility of the ER model is:

- It maps well to the relational model. The constructs used in the ER model can easily be transformed into relational tables.
- It is simple and easy to understand with a minimum of training. Therefore, the model can be used by the database designer to communicate the design to the end user.
- In addition, the model can be used as a design plan by the database developer to implement a data model in specific database management software.

ER Notation

There is no standard for representing data objects in ER diagrams. Each modeling methodology uses its own notation. The original notation used by Chen is widely used in academics texts and journals but rarely seen in either CASE tools or publications by non-academics. Today, there are a number of notations used; among the more common are Bachman, crow's foot, and IDEFIX.

All notational styles represent entities as rectangular boxes and relationships as lines connecting boxes. Each style uses a special set of symbols to represent the cardinality of a connection. The notation used in this document is from Martin. The symbols used for the basic ER constructs are:

- **Entities** are represented by labeled rectangles. The label is the name of the entity. Entity names should be singular nouns.
- **Relationships** are represented by a solid line connecting two entities. The name of the relationship is written above the line. Relationship names should be verbs

- **Attributes**, when included, are listed inside the entity rectangle. Attributes which are identifiers are underlined. Attribute names should be singular nouns.
- **Cardinality** of many is represented by a line ending in a crow's foot. If the crow's foot is omitted, the cardinality is one.

Existence is represented by placing a circle or a perpendicular bar on the line. Mandatory existence is shown by the bar (looks like a 1) next to the entity for an instance is required. Optional existence is shown by placing a circle next to the entity that is optional.

MySQL Data Tables:

Admin Table:(Table name is admin)

This store admin personal and login details.

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	ID	int(5)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
2	AdminName	varchar(45)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
3	UserName	char(45)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
4	MobileNumber	bigint(11)			Yes	NULL		
5	Email	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
6	Password	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
7	AdminRegdate	timestamp			Yes	current_timestamp()		

Visitor Table: (Table name is tblvisitor)

This store the visitor details and admin remark

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
1	ID	int(5)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
2	FullName	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
3	Email	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
4	MobileNumber	bigint(11)			Yes	NULL		
5	Address	varchar(250)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
6	WhomtoMeet	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
7	Department	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
8	ReasontoMeet	varchar(120)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
9	EnterDate	timestamp			Yes	current_timestamp()		
10	remark	varchar(255)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL		
11	outtime	timestamp			Yes	NULL		ON UPDATE CURRENT_TIMESTAMP()

CHAPTER 5

IMPLEMENTATION AND SYSTEM DESIGN

After all phase have been perfectly done, the system will be implemented to the server and the system can be used.

SYSTEM DESIGN

The goal of the system testing process was to determine all faults in our project .The program was subjected to a set of test inputs and many explanations were made and based on these explanations it will be decided whether the program behaves as expected or not. Our Project went through two levels of testing

1. Unit testing
2. Integration testing

UNIT TESTING

Unit testing is commenced when a unit has been created and effectively reviewed .In order to test a single module we need to provide a complete environment i.e. besides the section we would require

- The procedures belonging to other units that the unit under test calls
- Non local data structures that module accesses
- A procedure to call the functions of the unit under test with appropriate parameters

1. Test for the admin module

- **Testing admin login form**-This form is used for log in of administrator of the system. In this form we enter the username and password if both are correct administration page will open otherwise if any of data is wrong it will get redirected back to the login page and again ask the details.

- **Report Generation:** admin can generate report from the main database.

INTEGRATION TESTING

In the Integration testing we test various combination of the project module by providing the input.

The primary objective is to test the module interfaces in order to confirm that no errors are occurring when one module invokes the other module.

CHAPTER 6

EVALUATION

Project URL: <http://localhost/cvms>

Login Page

Company Visitor Management System
(CVMS)

User Name

Password

[Forgotten Password?](#)

SIGN IN

Dashboard

The dashboard features a header with the CVMS logo, a search bar, and a user profile for 'Tester1'. A sidebar on the left lists navigation options: Dashboard, New Visitor, Manage Visitors, and Visitors B/w Dates. The main content area displays four visitor statistics cards: Today's Visitors (0), Yesterday Visitors (0), Last 7 Days Visitors (0), and Total Visitors Till Date (4). A footer note reads 'CVMS 2018. All rights reserved.'

Add Visitor Page

The 'Add New Visitors' form includes fields for Full Name, Email Input, Phone Number, Address, Whom to Meet, Department, and Reason To Meet. A 'Submit' button is located at the bottom of the form. The footer contains the text 'CVMS 2018. All rights reserved.'

Manage Visitor Page

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number...

Tester1

- Dashboard
- New Visitor
- Manage Visitors
- Visitors B/w Dates

S.NO	Full Name	Contact Number	Email	Action
1	Akash	2147483647	akash@gmail.com	✎
2	Rajesh Singh	8979897979	rajesh@gmail.com	✎
3	Mukesh	7897897979	mukesh@gmail.com	✎
4	Ayushman	7897974697	abc@gmail.com	✎

CVMS 2018. All rights reserved.

Update Visitor Page

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number...

Tester1

- Dashboard
- New Visitor
- Manage Visitors
- Visitors B/w Dates

Visitor Details

Full Name	Test
Email	test@gmail.com
Mobile Number	5656565656
Address	S-120 New Delhi
Whom to Meet	Mr. Birjesh
Department	Hr.Department
Reason to Meet	Some Paper work
Visitor Entering Time	2018-10-20 23:12:04
Outing Remark :	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 80px;"></div>

[Update](#)

CVMS 2018. All rights reserved.

Full Visitor Page

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number..

 Tester1 ▾

- Dashboard
- New Visitor
- Manage Visitors
- Visitors B/w Dates

Visitor Details

Visitors Remark has been Updated.

Full Name	Test
Email	test@gmail.com
Mobile Number	5656565656
Address	S-120 New Delhi
Whom to Meet	Mr. Birijesh
Department	Hr.Department
Reason to Meet	Some Paper work
Visitor Entering Time	2019-10-20 23:12:04
Outing Remark	hgfhgfhg
Out Time	2019-10-20 23:13:43

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Visitor Reports

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number..

 Tester1 ▾

- Dashboard
- New Visitor
- Manage Visitors
- Visitors B/w Dates

Between Dates Reports

From Date

To Date

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Between Dates Reports

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number..

 Tester1 ▾

Between Dates Reports Report from 2019-10-19 to 2019-10-20

S.NO	Full Name	Contact Number	Email	Action
1	Test	5656565656	test@gmail.com	

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Admin Profile

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number..

 Tester1 ▾

Update Admin Profile

Admin Name

Email Input

Phone Number

User Name

Admin Registration date

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Change Password

CVMS

Search by names & mobile number..

 Tester1 ▾

Change Admin Password

Current Password

New Password

Confirm Password

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Forgot Password

**Company Visitor Management System
(CVMS)**

Password Recovery

Email Address

Mobile Number

[Sign in](#)

Reset Password

Company Visitor Management System
(CVMS)

Reset your Password

New Password

Confirm Your Password

RESET

[Sign in](#)

CHAPTER 7

CONCLUSION:

This Application provides a computerized version of Company Visitor Management System which will benefit the company.

It makes entire process online and can generate reports. It has a facility of staff's login where staff can fill the visitor details and generate report.

The Application was designed in such a way that future changes can be done easily. The following conclusions can be deduced from the development of the project.

- Automation of the entire system improves the productivity.
- It provides a friendly graphical user interface which proves to be better when compared to the existing system.
- It gives appropriate access to the authorized users depending on their permissions.
- It effectively overcomes the delay in communications.
- Updating of information becomes so easier.
- System security, data security and reliability are the striking features.
- The System has adequate scope for modification in future if it is necessary.

CHAPTER 8

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